

Emoji-Fy Create Your Own Emoji

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Abstract— Emojis are little graphics that are commonly used in text messages on social networking platforms. A current style of communication is created by combining visual and written content in the same message. Emoji, often known as avatars, are a form of nonverbal communication. These signs have become a crucial component of online conversation, product reviews, brand sentiment, and other activities. It's also prompted a surge in data science research towards emoji-based storytelling. It is now possible to determine human emotions from photographs thanks to advances in computer vision and in-depth research. We will categorise human facial expressions in this Deep Learning research in order to filter and map appropriate emojis or avatars. This project isn't meant to solve a real-world problem; rather, it allows us to experiment with new ideas.

Keywords—facial expression, deep learning learning, avatar, emoji, modern way of communication, human emotion

I. INTRODUCTION

Do people use emojis on a daily basis? Emojis have evolved into a new language that may more efficiently represent an idea or feeling. This visual language has become the de facto standard for online communication, appearing not only on Twitter but also on Facebook and Instagram. In today's generation, emoticons are commonly used to communicate with one another. As a result, we decided to create our own emojis. Emoji-Fy is a piece of software that allows you to create emoji and avatars. The neural network is an emerging application in various fields as an example of end-to-end learning. To recognise face emotions, we're developing a convolutional neural network.

For detecting human faces in photographs and videos, several methods have been proposed, which can be split into four categories: knowledge-based, feature-based, template-based, and form-based. When these methods are utilised in isolation, they will not be able to tackle all of the challenges associated with face recognition, such as position, expression, and orientation. As a result, it's a good idea to try a few different approaches in order or in simultaneously. The majority of today's facial recognition software focuses on recognising the five fundamental emotions: happiness, sorrow, fear, anger, and contempt.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Darwin [1] was the first to suggest that some of these faces Emotion expressions have their origin in the evolution of the human species. These facial expressions helped sentient beings to live because It looked like social animals like humans or necessary Chimpanzees are given expression of these imminent behaviors through the emotions so that they fight, conflict, Allowing disagreement, danger or comfort, approach, and so on here.

III. METHODOLOGY

In simple words, facial expressions are an arrangement of facial muscles that indicate a specific emotional state to the viewer. Anger, contempt, fear, happiness, sorrow, surprise, and neutral are the six basic kinds of emotions.

However, these expressions of emotions are not able Modification through social learning.

Ekman, Friesen [2] observed the facial muscles which are important in expressing emotion and made their findings to a system of 46 action units (AUs). These action units were crucial in reading human face expressions, as some of them raised and lowered the inner and outer brows. Prior to the publishing of this approach, face Expression research relied mostly on human classification of Example expressions, and many researchers were concerned about bias owing to the labeler's emotional state at the moment. When Ekman and Feisen's facial movement coding system was announced in 1977, it was quickly adopted as the gold standard.

In 2004, Paul Viola, Michael Jones [3] developed an extremely efficient face detector with high performance by using an adaboost learning algorithm to classify features derived from Haar-like features. Wang et al. used this approach to categorise faces into one of seven archetypal facial expressions, and found that it worked 92.4 percent of the time. Using hair features in combination with the Ada Boost boosting approach was at least two orders of magnitude quicker than using traditional classification SVMs and Gabor filters, according to White Hill and Omlin's research, with no noticeable performance loss.

More recently, work by Happy et al. [4] found this out in 2015 The Viola-Jones algorithm was not directly valuable recognition of emotions, but as a pre-processing step too Efficient recognition of the most important facial regions (e.g. lip corners and eyebrow edges), which were then further removed processed with local binary pattern histograms. Her Solution works similar to other prior art methods, but required far less computing time.

Chairunnisa and Benedictus (2017) [5], said that people hope the other person understands their feelings, ideas and impressions even though they are not communicating face-to-face, which emojis enable and make communication effective and understandable.

IV. MOTIVATION

Face Emoji Recognizer is a user-facing programme that detects a person's emotion in video shot by the camera. The one with the appropriate smiling The individual in the video's facial expression is presented on the screen, which varies as the expressions change. The HAAR face recognition classifier is implemented, as well as the CNN algorithm for expression recognition and two functions: relu and soft max (these are activity features).

We'll start by making our image black and white.

For each individual pixel, we want to look at the pixels that directly surround it.

Figure 1: Life cycle of emoji-fy

To turn a face into an emoji in real time, a face must first be identified and isolated from the background. Recognize all important features of the face. In the context of facial markers, our goal is to detect important facial structures on the face using shape prediction methods.

The entire method is a 3-step process:

1. Identify the face in the image.
2. Detect the key facial structures from the face.
3. Convert facial features to a real-time emoji.

A. Identify the face in the image

Dlib employs a mix of HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradient) and SVM (Support Vector Machine) trained on positive and negative pictures for face detection (meaning there are images with faces and those without faces).

Steps it follows:

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step in the fake news detection. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

2. Load model

```
model = load_model("model.h5")
```

3. captures frame and returns boolean value and captured image

```
cap = cv2.VideoCapture(0)
while True:
    ret, test_img = cap.read()
    if not ret:
        continue
    gray_img = cv2.cvtColor(test_img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2RGB)
```

4. cropping region of interest i.e. face area from image

```
for (x, y, w, h) in faces detected:
    cv2.rectangle(test_img, (x, y), (x + w, y + h), (255, 0, 0), thickness=7)
    roi_gray = gray_img[y:y + w, x:x + h]
    roi_gray = cv2.resize(roi_gray, (224, 224))
    img_pixels = image.img_to_array(roi_gray)
    img_pixels = np.expand_dims(img_pixels, axis=0)
    img_pixels /= 255
```

- Left eye
- Nose
- Jaw

5. find max indexed array

```
max_index = np.argmax(predictions[0])
emotions = ('angry', 'disgust', 'fear', 'happy', 'sad', 'surprise', 'neutral')
predicted_emotion = emotions[max_index]
cv2.putText(test_img, predicted_emotion, (int(x), int(y)), cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX, 1, (0, 0, 255), 2)
resized_img = cv2.resize(test_img, (1000, 700))
cv2.imshow("Facial emotion analysis", resized_img)
```

6. wait until 'q' key is pressed

```
if cv2.waitKey(10) == ord('q'):
    break
cap.release()
cv2.destroyAllWindows
```

```
import os
import cv2
import numpy as np
from keras.preprocessing import image
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
from keras.preprocessing.image import load_img, img_to_array
from keras.models import load_model
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
```

VI. RESULT

In the image below, sample output is the window where the user expressions are captured by the webcam and the corresponding emotions are recognized.

The relevant emoji appears on the left side of the screen when the emotion is identified. This emoji changes in response to the person's expression in front of the webcam. As a result of the modification, the individual in front of the webcam's countenance has changed. As

a result, this real-time application is extremely useful in a variety of disciplines such as psychology, computer science, linguistics, neurology, and others.


```
1/1 [=====] - 0s 97ms/step
🤔angry
1/1 [=====] - 0s 113ms/step
🤔angry
1/1 [=====] - 0s 114ms/step
😲surprise
1/1 [=====] - 0s 84ms/step
😊happy
1/1 [=====] - 0s 94ms/step
😲surprise
1/1 [=====] - 0s 102ms/step
😨fear
1/1 [=====] - 0s 74ms/step
```

VII. APPLICATION

Emotion-sensitive HCI interfaces can be created using robust spontaneous expression recognizers that can be constructed and given in real-time systems. The project has the potential to improve our daily lives by changing how we connect with computers and our surroundings in normal living and working environments. Our system's performance has improved significantly as a result of the high rate of proper recognition. Under the conditions of face registration error and quick processing time, promising results are produced.

The system is entirely automated and can handle both video and picture feeds. It has the ability to recognise and understand spontaneous comments. Our method can be utilised in digital cameras that only capture images of people who are smiling or who are not blinking their eyes. He displays himself in security systems that can identify a person in some type of expression. As people enter a room, the lights and televisions can be adjusted to fit their preferences.

This can be used by doctors to understand the pain intensity or illness of a deaf patient.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We decided to create our own emojis because today's age appreciates the trend of communicating using non-verbal indicators like emoticons. We will be able to discern human emotions from photographs thanks to breakthroughs in computer vision and deep learning. We will classify human facial emotions in this deep learning research in order to filter and map corresponding emojis or avatars. Emojify's use in the chat realm is the predicted outcome. We want people to be able to interact using their own emoticon that they may

customise. The project detects the current emotion and transforms the corresponding emoji so that the consumer receives an emoji of their face that they may use in conversation.

To anticipate people's emotions and depict them with emoticons, a human emotion detector employing emoticons is suggested using machine learning and Python. This involves image capture, image pre-processing, face identification, feature extraction, classification, and finally, when the emotions have been identified, the system assigns a specific piece of music to the user based on his emotions. The live footage acquired by the camera is the focus of our system..

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